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Antimicrobial fish therapy effect on water quality of aquaculture biofloc system

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Water quality of aquaculture biofloc systems has been evaluated on tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in several conditions. However, there is no information about an eventual introduction of antimicrobial molecules on water quality by metaphylaxis fish therapy in this aquaculture system. We evaluated water quality parameters of biofloc system with Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) submitted to antimicrobial metaphylaxis therapy. For this, two treatments were established: biofloc system with (BFTAT) or without (BFT) antimicrobial therapy. Each treatment group was composed by four 4m³-tanks replicates with 80 all-male tilapia (145.9 ± 0.86g) by tank. Antimicrobial therapy in BFTAT group was conducted by handing inclusion of FF-50[®], a commercial antimicrobial for aquaculture purposes (20mg of Florfenicol.day⁻¹ by kg of biomass as a final dose), vehicled with soybean oil on diet during ten consecutive days. Meanwhile, the BFT group only received feed with the same quantity of soybean oil inclusion during the same period of time. After therapy, all eight tanks were feed and handled in similar conditions during twenty additional days. Water quality parameters were evaluated as follow: temperature (C°) and dissolved oxygen (mg.L⁻¹), two times a day by Oxyguard[®] instrument; total ammonia nitrogen (mg.L⁻¹) and dissolved nitrite (mg.L⁻¹), twice a week by spectrophotometry; pH and salinity (g.L⁻¹), twice a week by Hanna[®] instrument; dissolved nitrate (mg.L⁻¹), at the onset and end of the experiment (experimental day one and thirty, respectively) by spectrophotometry; alkalinity (mg of CaCO₃.L⁻¹), once a week by titration procedure; settleable solids (ml.L⁻¹) and total solids (g.L⁻¹) once a week by Imhoff cone and filtration (100 µm-filters), respectively. Repeated measures ANOVA analysis (by SPSS[®] software) showed no significance difference between treatment

groups (P -value >0.05) for temperature ($28.1\pm 0.06^{\circ}\text{C}$), dissolved oxygen ($4.84\pm 0.03\text{mg.L}^{-1}$), total ammonia nitrogen ($0.17\pm 0.02\text{mg.L}^{-1}$), dissolved nitrite ($0.27\pm 0.03\text{mg.L}^{-1}$), pH (7.09 ± 0.03), salinity ($2.13\pm 0.01\text{g.L}^{-1}$), dissolved nitrate ($176.45\pm 10.55\text{mg.L}^{-1}$), alkalinity ($130.83\pm 3.82\text{mg.L}^{-1}$), total solids ($0.27\pm 0.01\text{g.L}^{-1}$) and settleable solids ($13.2\pm 0.78\text{mL.L}^{-1}$). Meanwhile, there were a significance variation of several water parameters across the time, which suggest an environment or tank effect. The results suggested that metaphylaxis therapy with florfenicol applied on Nile tilapia reared in biofloc technology do not induce detrimental effect on the water quality parameters.

Keywords: florfenicol, tilapia, biofloc system, water quality, aquaculture